

THE ROLE OF CREATIVE THINKING IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF CREATIVITY

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Abstract. *The work is devoted to the study of creative thinking in the creativity of clothing. The study of the main parameters of creativity: fluency, flexibility, originality, development, problems of temperament, thinking, the study of the intellect of the mind and provocation. Such concepts as "creativity", "creativity" are considered. Creativity in the work of designers of Uzbekistan, taking into account national traditions, ornament and color of fabrics and the prospects for their development.*

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Each person has the makings necessary to find creative ideas to a greater or lesser extent, which we do not use to our full potential. Everyone has their own bar, the goal to which you can and should strive. Special technologies and techniques make it possible to discover the existing hidden creative abilities. Humans have one marvelous flaw—we are incapable of making perfect copies.

Creative thinking research began to expand in the second half of the 20th century. The first diagnostic tasks were compiled, revealing the level of development of creative thinking. The processes of creativity of children and adolescents began to be experimentally studied. The first curricula for the formation of creative abilities were developed. At this time, the psychological components of creative activity were revealed: the flexibility of the mind; systematic and consistent thinking; dialectic; readiness for risk and responsibility for the decision made.

One of the fundamental principles of updating the content of education is its personal orientation, which implies reliance on the subjective experience of students, the actual needs of each student. In this regard, the question arose of organizing active cognitive and creative activity of students, contributing to the accumulation of creative experience of schoolchildren, as a basis, without which the self-realization of the individual at the subsequent stages of education becomes ineffective. Throughout the 20th century, the problem of creative potential has been studied from different angles. The modern rhythm of life forces us to learn new things every day, different methods develop consciousness and creative energy, which are taken into account and used in practice.

Albert Einstein gave the world the theory of relativity - this is well known. However, few people know that his brain of genius invented one of the most brilliant techniques for developing creativity.

This requires a calm environment conducive to creativity. Let it be any mechanical action - so, for example, Einstein played the violin and thought. The great physicist, as it turned out, had practically no internal dialogues. According to him, the truth appeared in visual images, creativity - in the connection of phenomena. Try to think in images, find solutions through the visualization of the problem.

Salvador Dali achieved excellent results thanks to one tricky visualization technique. The artist often fell asleep in an armchair, holding a spoon in his hand, which, at the moment of relaxation, fell into an aluminum plate and woke him up. He considered the moment between sleep and wakefulness priceless - it was then that famous images and paintings were born.

A creative wave can overtake you at the most inopportune moment when we do not have the opportunity to write down the idea.

James Altucher suggests making a positive habit of writing down at least 10 ideas a day. To do this, you always need to have a small chest notebook and a pen, as well as take notes on your phone. The most important thing is not to miss a tiny glimpse of creativity, because something worthwhile can come out of it.[1]

Psychologist and writer Edward de Bono solved the problem of the scarcity of ideas simply. In his opinion, creative tasks are the result of the emergence of human thinking from a rigid model of perception of reality. So, the solution can be found by asking unexpected, provocative questions.

"A thousand bad ideas you've tried are better than one great idea you never thought of doing." - Alfred Nobel

Any statement must be questioned by asking yourself questions and according to the level of development of which one can judge the degree of creativity of a particular person.

Fluency is the ability to come up with a wide variety of ideas at high speed.

Flexibility is the ability to assess a problem from all sides and apply different strategies in solving it.

Originality - the ability to generate non-standard or unexpected ideas, deviate from the generally accepted pattern.

Elaboration is the ability not only to generate ideas, but also to deepen and detail them. A high level of detail distinguishes inventors and designers.

To date, psychology uses the parameters of creativity proposed by D. Guilford, an American scientist who has been actively involved in the problems of temperament, thinking, the study of the intellect of the mind and provocation.

- Emotional assessment of the environment. A person is sensitive to the processes taking place around, passes them through emotions, is not a soulless witness. At the same time, his reaction to events is not only lively, but also adequate.

- Out of the box thinking. The individual is disconnected from existing stereotypes and patterns: he knows about their existence, but does not blindly accept them. The perception of the material world in such a person is fresh and direct, like that of a child. Thinking creatively often means thinking wrong and atypically.

- Ability to take justified risk. A creative person must have the courage not only to express his own opinion, but also to express it out loud, to say that it is not the sun that revolves around the earth, but vice versa. Expressing a revolutionary idea, the individual understands that it may not be confirmed, or will not be accepted in society.

- Versatility. "A talented person is talented in everything." Non-standard thinking, the search for new forms of creating things and phenomena is manifested in all spheres of human life. Going beyond the usual occurs at work, at home, and in the realization of needs. In any field, the individual thinks creatively.

- Independence. Creativity presupposes self-confidence and independence from the opinions of others and judgments prevailing in society. A person whose self-esteem depends on the approval of other people finds it difficult to come up with unusual ideas, because he is afraid of being criticized. A self-confident person will not be harmed by public condemnation.

- Curiosity, breadth of interests. If a person is not interested in the nature of the origin of things and phenomena, he is not capable of alternative solutions, taking on faith what is accepted in society. Creative individuals are distinguished by curiosity, they are often compared to children who have just begun to explore the world.

- Ability to focus, perseverance. Despite the playfulness and liveliness of the mind, such people are capable of concentration and have perseverance. The introduction of creative ideas requires perseverance, the ability to bring things to the end. Man is a pioneer, he does not have ready-made paths.

- High degree of autonomy. The listed properties of a creative personality (independence, high self-esteem) determine the possibility of its autonomy from other people and circumstances. These people are holistic inside, although they can be both extroverts and introverts.

- Healthy mind. A high level of emotionality in a creative person gets along well with a healthy psyche. This is another difference from famous creative people, many of whom suffered from manifestations of an unstable psyche.

In external manifestations, such personalities are usually very bright, with a good sense of humor, as they say, "in plain sight". A creative person attracts other people, it is interesting with him, he knows how to abstract from troubles and help find a non-standard way out of impasses. As a rule, among such people there are no whiners and complainers, their distinguishing feature is optimism.

Consider the content of the concepts of "creativity", "creativity", "creative abilities". In the modern lexicon, in the media and in professional circles, fashionable terminologies are increasingly common as: creativity "creativity", "creative abilities"

Creativity is the activity of the system, in the course of which it uses personal capabilities to create new useful systems, improve existing ones, or destroy harmful ones. The main difference between creative activity and practical activity is the uniqueness of the result. The consequences of creativity are difficult to predict and almost impossible to obtain.

The same result, even if the same process is repeated with the same initial conditions [3, p. 15]. The main means for performing creative activity is a special creative thinking - creativity. For the first time, the concept of "creativity" was used in 1922 by D. Simpson [3, p. 156]. With this term, he designated the ability of a person to abandon stereotypical ways of thinking. In its most general form, creativity is understood as a general ability to be creative.

Creativity (from Latin *creatio* - creation) is the ability of a person to generate unusual ideas, find original solutions, deviate from traditional patterns of thinking [5, p. 247-248]. So, K. Rogers (1994) understands creativity as the ability to discover new ways of solving problems and new ways of expression. Despite the fact that a large and meaningful material has been accumulated on the study of creativity, which has given certain results both in theoretical and practical terms,

there is still no unified and coherent theory of creativity, just as there is no identical definition of it and methods recognized by all. diagnosing this ability [3, p. 157].

Design is a figurative artistic design of something that does not yet exist and did not exist in nature or in culture, but which could arise. In the dictionary, the word "design" is translated both as an idea, intent, plan, goal, intention, and as a creative idea, plan, project, and as a drawing, calculation, design, and as design, design, and as a sketch, drawing, pattern, composition, and as the art of composition and even a work of art [4, p. 157]. In our understanding, the term "design" means the artistic design of industrial products, comfortable and beautiful things, the creation of a holistic subject environment, the modernization of products in accordance with the requirements of the dominant fashion based on scientific knowledge and technical achievements. According to P. Torrance and supporters of his approach, creativity consists of a set of abilities. They allow you to clearly understand how creativity manifests itself and what is needed for its development. These abilities include: fluency, originality, flexibility, openness, receptivity, imagery, abstractness, detail, verballity, stress tolerance.

Design provides complete freedom in the choice of technique and material for the execution of a creative idea. It involves the use of non-standard drawing techniques and their active mixing. Design-projecting is an interesting activity for children and has an invaluable role in the development of thinking, imagination and the ability to apply the acquired knowledge in practice.

Making one or another design project, pupils get acquainted with its purpose, individual elements, its use in everyday life, accumulate knowledge and skills acquired in various subject areas. This contributes to the disclosure and development of the creative potential of each child, in the process of activity they have an interest in artistic culture, primary information about it arises, students learn to relate creatively, with imagination and fantasy, to any work. According to many studies, the personality of the "ideal student" is opposite in its characteristics to the creative personality [4]. The generalized portrait of a student that teachers would like to work with is as follows: inquisitive, intelligent, thoughtful, sociable, sincere, kind, organized, disciplined, inventive. It is easy to see that all of the above results are united by one feature - insufficient orientation or underestimation of the teacher "the most common characteristic of all outstanding people" - craving for creativity (Maksimova S.V., 2006). Teachers give a clear preference to the intellectual characteristics of the individual, focusing more on his knowledge and learning opportunities than on creative abilities. A high percentage of choices is also noted in relation to those qualities that characterize a "problem-free" student, but say nothing about his creative inclinations and cognitive needs.

Among the qualities that describe the portrait of the "desired" student, only one - "inventive" - characterizes the actual creative possibilities. Characteristics such as "unusual", "independent", "unpredictable" were not among the "popular". It is interesting to note that among the most important qualities that a teacher working with gifted students should have, the features that characterize him as a creative person and a person who is able to see and appreciate the non-standard thinking of a student are also not included (Maksimova S.V., 2006). Such misunderstanding and underestimation of the most important link in the development of a gifted student does not allow us to hope for the success of a training program, no matter how well it is adapted to the needs and abilities of gifted students.

Unfortunately, attempts to stimulate the development of the creative potential of students began to be made not so long ago, and it is not yet clear which methods are the best. But research indicates that parents and educators should be more active in supporting creative pursuits that go beyond traditional academic disciplines. Providing such support (and, if possible, training with specialists) can help develop the creative potential of our future innovators, such as the following developments in clothing creativity.

Today, fashion dictates its own rules to everyone without exception. These are bold bright combinations, monochrome, unusual textures, interesting accessories.

Now it is very difficult to define the boundaries of such a concept as "Uzbek fashion". Costumes of the countries of Central Asia. - elegance, fine handwork and colors, cut, tailoring, color and of course fabric. Currently, projects are being planned to recreate hand embroidery on products, while preserving the color and traditional ornaments.

Fashion designer is a very creative profession. The person who has chosen it for himself should be distinguished by creativity and the ability to look at things from an unusual, unconventional side.

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